

Experimental validation of a model for T-bolt mechanical joints

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SUMMARY: T-bolts are widely used for joining thick laminates, especially at the root of large wind turbine blades, because of its good reproducibility and a lower cost than other joining procedures.

T-bolts are quite common for joining wood and wood-agglomerates; a transverse cylinder receives the load from the laminate and transfers it to a tension bolt, located in a hole done in the plane of the laminate. A high pretension is introduced at the bolts in order to assure the joint and for alleviating the fatigue on these bolts. This pretension introduces a compressive strain state in the laminate; therefore, classical failure analysis of mechanical joints must be modified to take it into account, because bearing failures are predominant, due to both, a reduced bearing surface and a more complex stress state compared to typical mechanical joints.

This paper describes the constitution and function of the different components of the joint, showing the different parameters that affect its performance, and presents a parametric analysis, useful for joint design and optimization, relating laminate thickness, bolt and cylinder diameters with pitch distance, and pretension of the bolt with external load. In order to provide information on the influence of the T-bolt geometry on the strength of the laminate in the net tension and bearing zones, tests for two different glass fiber - epoxy laminates, under different pitch/diameter ratios have been done, forcing either bearing or tension failure modes. Stress and strain concentrations in the laminate have been estimated through a three-dimensional finite element model that takes into account pretension effects and contact nonlinearities. How experimental results correlate with simple and finite element model analysis is discussed, and some conclusions are drawn.

KEYWORDS : Composite Joints, T-bolt, Experimental, Laminate failure.

INTRODUCTION

The figure 1 shows a sketch of the T-bolt joint, showing its main elements, as well as the main geometric parameters affecting its performance. As can be seen in the figure, the key parts of the joint (apart from the blade root laminate) are the **nut**, i.e. a steel cylinder placed transversally to the blade root laminate; and a highly pre-stressed **screw**, with one tip screwed to the nut, and the other one connected to the rotor hub by means of standard nuts. Before any external load is applied, the pretension of the screw (F_b) produces a high compression between the laminate and the hub flange (F_m) (figure 2a). In this starting situation, we have:

$$F_b = F_m = F_0$$

When an external tension load is applied, there is an increase in the tension of the screw and, at the same time, a reduction of the compression load acting between the laminate and the hub flange. In this case the equilibrium equation is:

$$F_b = P + F_m$$

Fig. 1 T-bolt connection

Therefore the variation of F_b will always be smaller than the external load applied (P) until F_m becomes 0 (*i.e.* the joint is opened). The ratio between the external load applied and the increment on F_b depends on the relative stiffness of the screw and the laminate according to the expression:

$$\Delta F_b = P_b = \frac{K_b}{K_b + K_m} P = \Phi P$$

where the Φ factor is typically between 0.16 and 0.25 for common joint designs. In the figure 3 a graphical representation of the former expression is shown.

Fig. 2 Free body diagram

Fig. 3 Rigging diagram

In all current designs, the weakest part of the joint is the screw, due, first, to the fact that this is by far the simplest and the most standard element and, therefore, the one which allows a more accurate sizing and, second, because it is the part of the joint easiest to replace in the casualty of a failure and, therefore, it is designed to be the mechanical “fuse” of the T-bolt. In wind turbines, the screw diameter (d in the figure 1) is typically determined by fatigue loads which, as already mentioned, are greatly reduced by pretensioning, nevertheless care should be taken not to use a too high pretension, because this could precipitate a static failure. Therefore pretension should be determined in such a way that $F_0 > (1 - \Phi)P$ for all fatigue loads (*i.e.* opening of the joint is not allowed for this kind of loads), while for the extreme load cases F_0 should be equal to or even slightly smaller than $(1 - \Phi)P$. The figure 4 represents the relation between the screw load and a cyclic external load for both cases.

Fig. 4 Screw load compared to external load

Regarding the nut diameter (D in the figure 1), although it has some influence on the laminate bearing strength, it is mainly determined by the strength of the nut itself. Therefore an estimation of the maximum stresses in this element, which can only be achieved using a 3D FE model, would be required. Nevertheless, a reasonable conservative estimation could be achieved considering the nut as a symmetric beam, with a uniform distributed load on the contact area and a uniform shear load on the screw threads. This simplified model leads to nut diameters of about 2 times the nominal screw diameter, i.e. $d/D = 0.5$, which is the typical value found in most T-bolt designs.

The rest of the geometric parameters, excepted the hub flange thickness (th) that is usually defined independently of any particular blade root design, depend mainly on the laminate strength and its different failure modes (bearing, net tension and shear).

Of them, the laminate edge to nut hole axis distance (e), related to the shear failure, is the less critical, because there is usually no problem in providing a sufficient value for this parameter, which can be assumed to be around $e = 2.5D$ for a quasi isotropic laminate.

When it comes to the laminate thickness (t), the main problem one has to face is the absolute lack of information related to the bearing strength of such thick laminates, containing a hole (the screw hole) in the centre of the bearing area. This forces the designer to oversize t in order to obtain a safe joint. For example, according to *Germanisher Lloyd* rules, the mean bearing stress is to be 100 MPa or less, giving to a typical thickness value of about $t = 1.5D$.

Eventually, hole spacing (w) is to be defined, which is probably the parameter that has the highest influence on the joint efficiency. This is due to the fact that, for a given blade root diameter, an increase in w , that gives a higher net tension strength, produces, at the same time, a relative reduction in all other strengths (i.e. the strengths of the screw, the nut or the laminate bearing strength). Therefore, attention must be paid to chose an optimum value for this parameter, which requires an accurate prediction of the laminate net tension strength. Again, little studies have been conducted in this subject [1] for the T-bolt geometry and, therefore, designers should rely either on experimental tests or on the design data available for overlap joints. This extrapolation from the overlap case is based in the fact that, in the net tension area, the influence of the screw hole is probably relatively small, although, so far, there are no published works confirming that point. A common design value for the w/D ratio is about 2, much smaller than for overlap joints, as a consequence of the reduced bearing strength of the T-bolt joint.

EXPERIMENTAL STRAIN DETERMINATION

In the introduction we have shown that there are still a lot of uncertainties in certain aspects of the T-bolt design and optimization processes, mainly related to the laminate strength. One of the first issues to address, in order to reduce the uncertainty level, is an accurate estimation and analysis of the stress and strain fields induced in the laminate around the joint area. A finite element model, featured in the previous ICCM conference, was therefore developed.

Details of the model are shown in [2], but in short, it can be said that it consists in a FE model based on tetrahedral eight node linear elements with full integration, the mesh is generated using a custom parametric meshing procedure (figure 5), the nut is modeled as a rigid cylinder and the screw as a linear elastic spring, the contact area is automatically determined by an iterative procedure based on direct imposition of displacement restrictions.

Fig. 5 Finite element mesh

In the first experimental model verification carried on using electric strain gauges, it was shown that, good correlation exists between numeric and experimental values. Nevertheless, some minor divergences were found that suggested the idea of performing a full field experimental strain analysis in order to better understand the sources of these divergences.

The analysis was performed using a dark field circular polariscopy, by which a series of fringes proportional to the maximum shear strain in the surface of a test specimen are generated. Photoelastic sheets of 1.2 mm in thickness provided by the *Measurements Group* were adhered to two T-bolt specimens, of 50 and 90 mm wide respectively, and made of a 36 mm thick glass epoxy laminate¹. The specimens were illuminated using a circular polarized light source and the reflected light was filtered through a quarter wave sheet and a polarizer before being recorded using a standard photographic camera.

The fringe factor of the photoelastic sheets used is $f = 1580$, therefore, the difference between the principal strains of each point of the surface would be:

$$\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2 = Nf$$

where N is the fringe order of that point and ε_1 and ε_2 are the principal strains at the same point expressed in micro deformations. When monochromatic light is used, the fringe order is incremented each time the light intensity vanishes due to a phase angle of 180 deg. between the two components of the polarized light. When white light is used, each wavelength vanishes at a different relative

¹ The geometry and material of the specimens is the same of the MN and MB specimens described in the next section of this paper.

retardation, and therefore a conventional fringe order is defined which is increased each time the light component with a wavelength of 575 nm (perceived by the human eye as green) is extinguished.

In the figure 6 the colors defining the fringe order transition are shown.

Fig. 6 Fringe orders

The figure 7 shows the contours obtained for the MN specimen under loads of 0, 10, 30 and 50 kN. It can be seen that, even in the unloaded case, some bright spots appear in the contact area, this is due to very slight irregularities present in the laminate. In the other load cases, the influence of such irregularities is also very clear, determining in a great measure the shape of the contour maps. Nevertheless as the load is increased contours appear to have a higher symmetry, which indicates a reduced influence of the surface irregularities.

Fig. 7 Photoelastic fringes, $w = 50$ mm

The figure 8 shows the pictures corresponding to the MB specimen under the same loads. In this case there are less bright spots in the unloaded case, which is probably due to a looser fitting between the nut and the laminate hole, more than to a smoother contact surface, as confirms the fact that the contours obtained for the loaded cases are even more unsymmetrical than in the former specimen.

Last, in the figure 9 the contours obtained by numerical simulations are compared to some contours extracted from the photoelastic pictures. As it was expected, in the numerical model, the extreme unsymmetrical strain concentrations are not present, leading to high divergences between predicted and measured deformations in points close to the contact area. Nevertheless, as the distance to the hole edge increases, differences become smaller.

Therefore, it is possible to state that the small differences detected between strains measured with electric strain gauges and the FE model are mostly due to the irregularities in the contact surface. Although it is theoretically possible to reduce the irregularity of the contact surface this would be hardly useful in practical designs whose manufacturing costs should be kept as lower as possible. Additionally, the high stress concentrations would probably disappear at loads close to the failure, as the small failure load dispersion found indicates.

Fig. 8 Photoelastic fringes, $w = 90 \text{ mm}$

Fig. 9 FEA – Photoelasticity comparison

FAILURE TESTS

A series of tests have been performed forcing either bearing or net tension failure of the laminate. Those tests have provided, amongst other results, the failure load of four different kinds of specimens which combined with the FE analysis of the same specimens can show the relation between the stress states in the T-bolt and its failure. Details of the experiments are provided in [3], therefore in this section only its main characteristics will be shown as well as the failure loads.

The specimens tested have been manufactured from two different material systems, provided by the companies *Aertusa* and *MTorres*, both of them Spanish blade manufacturers. Both materials are glass – epoxy laminates, although its mechanical properties are considerably different, because of the different manufacturing processes and base materials used.

The first of these materials, from now on referred as A, has been laminated by hand lay – up and cured in a vacuum bag using a resin from the German resin manufacturer *MGS* and a multidirectional

fabric from *Ahlstrom*. The stacking sequence is (-45,0,+45,90)_n, the fiber fraction 35%, and the average thickness of each group of layers (-45,0,+45,90) is about 0.8 mm.

The second one, that will be referred as M, has been obtained by automatic lay – up from a unidirectional prepreg from *SP* and cured in a vacuum bag. Its stacking sequence is (90,+45,0,-45,0)_{ns}, the weight fiber fraction obtained is 60% and the average thickness of each layer is 0.4 mm.

The table 1 shows the dimensions of the different specimens, according to the generic geometry shown in the figure 10.

Fig. 10 T-bolt specimens

Table 1 Dimensions of the specimens (in mm).

Identification	Specimens	D	d	W	th	e	L
AB	2	30	17.5	90	37	60	300
AN	4	30	17.5	50	37	60	300
MB	4	30	21	75	36	75	300
MN	4	30	16	48	36	75	300

Failure of the laminate in standard T-bolt designs is extremely improbable, because, as already mentioned, the screw acts as a fuse, reaching its yield limit and even its ultimate stress far before any of the laminate failure modes can appear. Therefore, either a special fixture capable of transferring high loads to the nut, or a “non standard” T-bolt design, with a larger and stronger screw are to be used, in order to obtain laminate failure. The first approach has been used for the AB, AN and MN tests where the load was transferred to the nut by a special steel fixture, while for the MB specimens a high strength 12.9 metric 21 screw was the responsible of the load transfer to the nut.

The table 2 shows the average ultimate load and bearing or net tension strength of each kind of specimen. Bearing strength (S_b) is determined dividing the ultimate load by the bearing area A_b defined by:

$$A_b = tD - \frac{\pi d^2}{4}$$

while the net tension strength is obtained the ultimate net tension load by A_n where:

$$A_n = t(w - D)$$

Table 2 Failure loads and stresses

	Failure	P_{\max} (kN)	S_b/S_n (MPa)
AB	Bearing	226.9	256
AN	Net tension	192.3	220
MB	Bearing	279.7	365
MN	Net tension	223.3	326

STRESS STATES AT FAILURE LOAD

In this section, the FE model briefly described formerly, has been applied to the geometry of the test specimens with an external load equal to the failure load.

The geometry of the specimens has already been described in the experimental section and the estimated elastic material properties are shown in table 3. The tensile strength in the main direction of the laminate are respectively 557 MPa for material M and 428 for material A.

Table 3 elastic material properties

Material	E_x	E_y	E_z	ν_{xy}	ν_{yz}	ν_{zx}	G_{xy}	G_{yz}	G_{zx}
A	18130	10315	7200	0.346	0.385	0.114	4776	2398	2658
M	25627	19572	11788	0.269	0.358	0.141	7785	4181	4423

In order to evaluate the influence of the stress concentrations on the bearing and net tension failure modes, stress in direction x (σ_x) has been plotted for the selected regions shown in figure 11. In the case of the net tension failure the A-B line has been selected because of the small variation of the stresses across the hole thickness of the specimen. In the case of the bearing failure the variation of the stresses through the thickness are much higher and, therefore the results have been plotted over the A-B-C-D area.

Fig. 11 Regions selected for result plots

In the figure 12 the results obtained for the net tension specimens (AN and MN) are shown. The maximum stress calculated in the hole surface is about a 25% higher than the tensile laminate stress in the case of the MN specimens and about a 30% higher in the case of the AN specimens what suggests that there is little stress relaxation compared to typical overlap joints. Nevertheless, in both cases, the stresses reach the tensile strength value approximately at 0.9 mm away from the hole surface, despite of the differences between both materials, what suggests that for glass – epoxy, quasi – isotropic, laminates it is possible to predict the net tension failure of the T-bolt using the Point Stress criterion [4,5] with a characteristic distance of 0.9 mm.

Fig. 12 Stresses along the A-B line, net tension specimens

In the figure 13 the results obtained for the bearing specimens are shown. As can be seen, the absolute values of the stresses hardly reach the tensile strength of the laminate (557 MPa) in the case of the MB specimen, while in the case of the AB specimen the maximum peak is only about 85% of the tensile strength of the laminate (428 MPa). Therefore, either the relation between the tensile stress and the compressive stress is not uniform in both laminates, or the Point Stress criterion is not applicable to the bearing case (with the same level of precision than in the net tension area). In order to further understand this point, accurate measurements of the compressive strength of the material are needed.

Fig. 13 Stresses on the A-B-C-D area, bearing specimens

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The T-bolt joint constitutes an attractive solution for the joining of composite laminates with metal components and even of two thick composite laminates. Among its advantages, a very high reliability and stability, and a low cost compared to other solutions should be mentioned, while its main disadvantage is a relatively small efficiency.

In order to improve the efficiency of the joint, it is necessary to fully understand the different failure modes of the laminate, providing experimental failure loads, describing failure mechanisms and formulating accurate failure prediction methods.

Therefore, a FE model has been developed, in order to predict the stress states in the laminate, this model has been verified with experimental measures, finding a good correlation between the model and the experiments, nevertheless, for low loads, it has been shown that there is a very high influence of small irregularities of the contact surface on the local strains near the hole edge, which can cause some divergences between point measures and FE results.

Furthermore an experimental program has been developed in order to obtain failure loads for both bearing and net tension failure modes. These failure loads have been then applied to FE models of the specimens in order to obtain a first approximation to the stress states present at failure which will provide some information for a later formulation of failure criteria. Thus, it has been shown that, a simple Point Stress criteria will probably provide accurate results using the laminate tensile strength and a characteristic length of about 0.9 mm. For the case of the bearing failure, this simple procedure, apparently, it is not of application, nevertheless further studies are needed in order to state whether the problems can be solved using accurate laminate compression strength data.

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